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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to use global position systems (GPS) to analyze the external loads of the three different acquisition training sessions (ATS) with competitive matches in professional soccer players over a six-week period. Sixteen professional soccer players participated in the study, which analyzed the distribution of external load during the training microcycle of a professional soccer team. The three types of ATS undertaken by the players were: ATS1 (strength), ATS2 (endurance), ATS3 (speed). The total distance covered, the distance covered at above $14 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, the distance covered $> 21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, the number of high accelerations ($>3 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) and player load were recorded. The results showed that external loads were consistently higher during matches when compared to all training sessions (range of effect sizes: 1.06 to 3.38). Between training session comparisons revealed higher external loads during ATS1 and ATS2, when compared to ATS3 (range of effect sizes: 0.60 to 2.41). The only external load variable that differed between ATS1 and ATS2 was the distance covered $> 21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, which was higher for ATS1. Our findings suggest that technical staff should consider the physical demands of weekly periodization in order to understand the training process with regard to optimizing player physical performance.

Key words: competition; team sport; training; performance.

INTRODUCTION

Professional soccer players cover approximately $120 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ during official matches (5,13,38), of which at least $10 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ takes place at high-intensity ($>19.8 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) (5) and almost $20 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ are covered at above $16 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ (13). Further, around 76 accelerations and 54 decelerations are performed by professional soccer players in a complete match with 36 AU of player load (PL) per min (16). The high physical match demands, hereon referred to as external load, imposed on players suggests matches to be

the most demanding session of the microcycle (29,30,39). It is therefore hardly surprising that current match schedule is influential for coaches when planning their teams' training strategies (40). To understand the dose-response nature of the training process and optimize players' performance, it is important not only to monitor match loads but also to quantify the external loads imposed by the weekly training microcycle. Coaches design the weekly microcycle with regard to specific soccer objectives (technical and tactical) while taking into account conditional dimensions in terms of external training load (30,39). It therefore seems appropriate to identify external training and match loads with the aim of ensuring appropriate training load distribution during the microcycle.

The microcycle is used in soccer to organize daily training components for each week of the in-season period (8,30,39). An appropriate distribution of training load can help soccer players achieve optimum match performance (17,35) while reducing the risk of injury caused by inadequate training load distribution (20,27). With the aim of prescribing appropriate external loads for soccer players through the microcycle, three types of training acquisition days (strength, endurance and speed) have been established to develop/maintain different physical capacities (8). Acquisition training sessions (ATS) are usually undertaken during the middle of the week (from Tuesday to Friday) and in an elite Premier League soccer team it was observed that during the first ATS (strength), players performed a greater number of accelerations and decelerations and were subject to higher levels of PL in comparison to the other training days (1). Buchheit et al. (8) observed that young elite soccer players covered a greater total distance and performed at a higher average speed during the second acquisition training day (endurance) with greater distance covered at sprint velocities ($>19.8 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) on the third acquisition day (8). However, other authors (29) have not observed this distribution of external load during the microcycle. Here, these authors reported a similar training load in all physical variables except high-speed distance on all training days, which decreased on the last training session. This disagreement suggests it is necessary to gain a better understanding of elite soccer teams' external training loads, as this will help develop specific training strategies aimed at competitive matches preparation.

Global positioning system (GPS) devices have been used extensively in the last few decades mainly for research purposes and most professional soccer teams use this technology during training (40). As such, some scientific studies have analyzed the differences in external load between specific training drills and friendly matches

(4,12,21). Nevertheless, as the Federation International of Associated Football (FIFA) did not allow GPS devices to be used in official competitions until the 2016/2017 season (26), it was not possible to use the same equipment to compare training and match loads. Matches were predominantly analyzed by tracking systems such as Amisco or Prozone (5,9,11), yet these systems were not available for training sessions. Therefore, the main aim of this study was to use GPS to analyze the external loads of the three different ATS with competitive matches in professional soccer players over a six-week period.

METHODS

Experimental Approach to the Problem

This investigation analyzed the distribution of external load during the microcycle of a professional soccer team. Although players trained at least four days per week and were involved in a weekend match (i.e., Sunday), the day after a match was excluded from the analysis due to the different training regimes of the players who were starters (recovery) and non-starters (compensatory training) and also because these sessions were not considered to be an ATS. The external loads produced by the players during eighteen ATS and six matches were collected during the 2016/2017 competitive period (January to February). Training sessions were carried out on the same playing surface (third generation artificial turf) and matches were played on four pitches with similar dimensions (100 x 64 m), comprising three matches at home and the other three matches away where four matches were won, one match drew, and one match lost.

Subjects

Sixteen professional soccer players (age: 21.0 ± 0.6 years, height: 180 ± 5 cm, body mass: 70.1 ± 6.8 kg, and body mass index: 21.6 ± 1.4 kg·m⁻²) participated in the study. Participants played in a reserve team of a club in the Spanish La Liga and they competed in the Spanish 2nd Division B during the 2016-2017 season. The team finished the regular season in 11th position (from twenty teams). All players who took part in the matches trained at least 80% of the training volume were selected for further analysis. Goalkeepers were not included in the study due to their specific demands. All the participants were informed of the procedures, methods, benefits, objectives and possibly risk involved in the study before giving their written consent. The study was performed in accordance

with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013) and approved by the Ethics Committee of Basque Country University (M10/2016/079).

Procedures

The typical ATS program for the six-week period (3 ATS per week) is shown in Table 1. Based on a previous study (8), which examined the representative three typical conditioned sessions (i.e., strength, endurance and speed) targeting on each of the three main physical capacities, we have adopted this soccer training periodization model. In Table 1, the individual interaction space (IIS) used in each ATS is shown to explain the horizontal alternation of conditional contents within the same typical training week. In this respect, ATS1 was focused on neuromuscular demands, ATS2 on the endurance components, and ATS3 on speed actions. Coaches only used the 1-4-4-2 system during matches. Prior to each match, players undertook a 20-min standardized warm-up, consisting of 7-min slow jogging and strolling locomotion followed by 10-min specific exercises (different passes in pairs and small-sided games involving 4 vs. 4 + 2 wildcard players) and finishing with 3 min of progressive sprints and accelerations. In each ATS, the warm-up followed a similar structure. All players were advised to follow a similar diet (55% calories derived from carbohydrate, 25% from fat, and 20% from protein) during the study.

*****Table 1 near here*****

Physical variables

The players' external loads were monitored using microsensor units containing a 10 Hz GPS and 100 Hz triaxial accelerometer (WIMU PRO™, RealTrack Systems, Almería, Spain) (3). To eliminate inter-unit variability, each player wore their own unit which was inserted into the manufacturer provided vest which holds the receiver tightly between the scapulae. In accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, the microsensor devices were activated 15 min before the start of each training session and match. Data were downloaded post-training/match and analyzed using a customized software package (WIMU SPRO, Almería, Spain). The total distance covered (in $\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), the distance

covered at and above $14 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ (in $\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), the distance covered at and above $21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ (in $\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), and the number of high accelerations ($>3 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, $\text{accelerations}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) were registered as indicators of external load (15,31). Additionally, PL ($\text{AU}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) was computed as the vector magnitude representing the sum of accelerations recorded in the anteroposterior, mediolateral, and vertical planes of movement. The reliability and validity of the WIMU microsensor units for our chosen external load metrics is reported elsewhere (3). Data were collected during good weather and satellite conditions for GPS (number of satellites = 10.1 ± 0.2) during ATS and matches.

Statistical Analysis

Results are presented as mean \pm standard deviations (SD). Given the within-subject, repeated measures nature of our research design, we adopted the approach of summary measures (32). Here, the summary measure chosen was the mean player ATS and match response. As such, each player provided a mean value for each of the external load variables. A visual inspection of the residual plots revealed no substantial evidence of heteroscedasticity; therefore, all analyses were performed on the raw data. Between-session comparisons on the mean player responses were analyzed using a custom-made spreadsheet (24). Effect sizes (for each comparison: mean difference / pooled standard deviation) were used to assess the magnitude of all between-session differences (ATS1, ATS2, ATS3, matches), with magnitude classified as trivial (<0.2), small ($0.2\text{--}0.6$), moderate ($0.6\text{--}1.2$), large (≥ 1.2) (25). The uncertainty of the effect sizes estimates is represented by 90% confidence intervals. Effect sizes were then qualified using probabilistic terms and assigned using the following scale: 25–75%, possibly; 75–95%, likely; 95–99.5%, very likely; $>99.5\%$, most likely (25). The coefficients of variation (CV) was used to assess the variability of the each ATS throughout the 6-week period by the formula $\text{CV} = (\text{SD}\cdot\text{mean}^{-1}) \times 100$. Given the relatively small size of our study, both number of players and number of sessions/ matches, we employed a conservative approach to inference whereby only $\text{ES} \geq \text{moderate}$ were deemed meaningful.

RESULTS

The external loads recorded by the players during ATS and matches during the six-week competitive period are shown in Table 2.

*****Table 2 near here*****

With the exception of high accelerations (ATS1 and ATS2 only), match external loads were greater when compared to ATS1, ATS2, and ATS3 (magnitude: moderate to large (Figure 1). External loads recorded during ATS1 and ATS2, with the exception of distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and distance $>14 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively, were greater when compared to ATS3 (moderate to large) (Figure 2). The only meaningful difference in external load between ATS1 and ATS2 was a moderately higher distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ during ATS1.

*****Figure 1 near here*****

*****Figure 2 near here*****

DISCUSSION

The main aim of this study was to analyze the external load imposed on professional soccer players during three different types of ATS and competitive matches across a six-week period. Since the literature is equivocal regarding the distribution of external load during the microcycle in professional soccer teams (1,8,30), results obtained from our study can help us understand training week periodization in a Spanish professional team. The main results showed that for almost all measures external loads were higher during matches when compared to ATS. When comparing between ATS, external loads were consistently higher for ATS1 and ATS2 when compared to ATS3.

Quantifying the physical demands of soccer players during matches enables provides specific information for the design of training programs (29). In our study, match total distance was higher than that reported in other studies of elite soccer players (163 ± 134 vs. $\sim 120 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) (5,13,38). This could be because all players who participated in the matches (starters and non-starters) were included as part of the statistical analysis in our study. With respect to the match distance covered at medium and high intensities, while distance $>14 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was similar (24 ± 11 vs. $\sim 20 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) to other studies (5,38), our distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was higher than the results obtained in other studies of players in the Spanish First Division (14) and Champions League (6). It seems that soccer players at

higher competitive levels do not cover greater total distance or greater distance at high-intensity effort levels, possibly due to the style of game (5). Moreover, regarding short-term actions, some authors reported ~25 high-intensity ($>3 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) accelerations per min in international players (36) and a PL value of $36 \text{ AU}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ in elite Norwegian soccer players (16). However, we observed ~11 high-intensity ($>3 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) accelerations and PL $22 \pm 17 \text{ AU}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ in Spanish 2^a B soccer players. Therefore, although total distance and distance covered at high intensity is greater in players at lower competitive levels, it seems that high-intensity short-term actions are typical of players at higher competitive levels. So, it would be interesting to analyze whether high-intensity short-term actions could discriminate between players of different standard of play.

The results obtained for ATS and match external loads should, however, be interpreted with some caution due to the high session CV's (range = 10 to 100%). Our results agree with those reported by Thorpe et al. (39) who observed a similar CV value in English Premier League soccer players for high-intensity running ($> 14.4 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) during each ATS. Focusing on matches, although we have observed a CV of 22.5% for total distance, other studies showed lower CV values, mostly explained by the higher number of matches registered (23,33). Conversely, for distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ a CV of 36% has been found in elite players in five friendly matches (12), 60% in professional players in 34 matches (33), 60% in young players in three official matches (19), and 20% in elite players during one full season (22). Very high session CV's were also observed in our study for distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and for the number of high accelerations, which is similar to those reported by other authors investigating high-intensity actions (23,33). These high CV's suggest that ATS and matches register different external loads, mainly due to contextual factors such as the score, the level of the opposition, competitive-level and/or soccer drills (7,10,14) which can influence the physical patterns of the players. For this reason, further research should include consideration of the session variability in addition to the external loads recorded during ATS and competitive matches.

Our results showed large to moderate differences in certain physical variables (i.e., total distance, distance $>14 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and PL) between matches and training days (ATS1, ATS2, and ATS3). Previous studies also reported higher total distance and running distance at high-intensities in friendly match-play than specific training drills (e.g., small- and large-sided games) (12,21). However, our study is the first to compare the external load between official matches and each ATS. The results obtained in our

study show that official matches are the most demanding (highest external load) session during the microcycle. The incidence of higher external loads in matches in comparison to ATS has also been found using other objective methods which measure internal loads (2,37) and from subjective methods such as rating of perceived exertion (RPE) (28). However, in the present study non-meaningful differences were found in the number of high accelerations between ATS1 and ATS2 compared to matches. Other studies also reported more short-term actions (accelerations and decelerations) in small-sided games than in match-play (4,21). Therefore, it seems that the use of specific soccer tasks (small- or large-sided games) can elicit a similar or higher number of high-intensity short-term actions than matches. Further research could analyze whether the similar number of accelerations registered in ATS1 and ATS2 in comparison with matches is positive or negative in optimizing physical performance or reducing injury risk.

Knowledge of external load distribution strategies during the weekly microcycle of a professional team could help technical staff to understand the training process for optimizing athletes' performance (18,34). Therefore, the principle objectives, in terms of conditional capacities of each training session, play an important role in the training load distribution (8). In our study, moderate to large differences were found for high accelerations and PL for ATS1 and ATS2 when compared to ATS3. Such results seem to emphasize that coaches in this professional soccer team use a specific strategy for ATS1 (strength) focusing on more high-intensity short-term actions. Likewise, Akenhead et al. (1) observed the highest PL value in professional players, as well as the largest total number of accelerations and decelerations, during the same training session (strength). However, a moderately higher distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was recorded during in ATS1 when compared ATS2. These results are not in line with those obtained by Buchheit et al. (8) who observed the highest distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ during ATS3 (speed). Nevertheless, in our study non-meaningful differences were found between the sprinting distances covered between ATS1 and ATS3. Conversely, although Buchheit et al. (8) reported higher total distance during ATS2, non-meaningful differences were observed between ATS1 and ATS2 in our study. Additionally, the present study showed the highest external loads during strength and endurance training sessions, with the exception of distance $>21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and distance $>14 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively, were greater when compared to ATS3 (speed). Our results suggest that coaches of this professional team use a strategic distribution of external load based on the different training sessions of ATS1 (strength), ATS2

(resistance), and ATS3 (speed). Given that professional soccer teams use similar strategies of periodization during the microcycle, it would be interesting to know how effective this periodization is for match preparation and also to assess the effect on conditional capacities.

In conclusion, the results showed that almost all measures external loads were higher during matches when compared to ATS. When comparing between ATS, external loads were consistently higher for ATS1 and ATS2, when compared to ATS3. Therefore, physical demands of weekly periodization should be considered by technical staff to understand the training process with regard to optimizing athletes' performance.

PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

Given the aforementioned differences between soccer matches and ATS, and among ATS, specific strategies for the distribution of external load, based on the different training sessions such as ATS1 (strength), ATS2 (resistance), and ATS3 (speed), would be implemented by the professional team coaches to optimize player physical performance. Specifically, two relevant aspects should be taken into account by practitioners: 1) high session-to-session variability suggests the need to establish homogeneous training sessions throughout the in-season period to help avoid excessive training load fluctuations that may be associated with injury risk, and 2) technical staff should approach their training tasks in each specific ATS to get the conditional objectives in terms of neuromuscular demands (e.g., high accelerations and player load), endurance components (e.g., total distance and distance covered at above $14 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) and speed actions (e.g., distance covered at above $21 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$). Through this weekly distribution players could replicate the external demands required during official matches, and thus optimize match preparation.

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Table 1. Distribution of acquisition training sessions' (ATS) contents of a typical weekly program during the six-week competitive period.

	ATS1 (strength) MD+3	ATS2 (endurance) MD-3	ATS3 (speed) MD-1	Match
Task 1	Positional games (IIS = <150 m ²)	Positional games (IIS = >150 m ²)	Positional games (IIS = <50 m ²)	
Task 2	Small sided game (IIS = <150 m ²)	Large sided game (IIS = >200 m ²)	Large sided game (IIS = >200 m ²)	Competitive match
Task 3	Medium sided game (IIS = 150-200 m ²)	Simulated 11 vs. 11 game (IIS = 300 m ²)	Tactical drills and free kicks	
Duration (min)	75-90	75-90	50-70	90

Note: IIS: individual interaction space; MD: match day.

Table 2. Mean \pm SD and session CV (%) obtained for the physical variables during the acquisition training sessions (ATS1, ATS2 and ATS3) and competitive matches.

Variables	ATS1	CV (%)	ATS2	CV (%)	ATS3	CV (%)	Match	CV (%)
Total distance (m.min ⁻¹)	78.3 \pm 6.4	8.7	80.9 \pm 7.5	9.7	61.2 \pm 8.4	14.2	163 \pm 34	22.5
Distance>14 (m.min ⁻¹)	10.1 \pm 2.0	20.8	9.3 \pm 2.1	26.1	8.2 \pm 3.9	54.5	24 \pm 11	46.4
Distance >21 (m.min ⁻¹)	5.6 \pm 3.0	65.1	3.5 \pm 1.9	94.2	3.8 \pm 2.1	100.2	12.2 \pm 6.2	89.5
High accelerations (acc.min ⁻¹)	0.10 \pm 0.04	50.6	0.11 \pm 0.04	58.3	0.06 \pm 0.03	71.8	0.13 \pm 0.09	77.0
Player Load (AU.min ⁻¹)	8.6 \pm 0.8	10.5	8.5 \pm 0.9	10.9	6.6 \pm 0.8	13	22 \pm 17	60.2

Note: SD: standard deviation; CV: coefficient of variation; Distance>14: distance covered at above 14 km·h⁻¹; Distance>21: distance covered at above 21 km·h⁻¹.

Figure 1. Forest plot showing the effect sizes (with associated confidence intervals) for the external load comparisons between acquisition training sessions (ATS) and matches. The shaded area, spanning -0.6 to 0.6, represents unmeaningful effect sizes. * Possibly; ** Likely; *** Very Likely; **** Most Likely.

Figure 2. Forest plot showing the effect sizes (with associated confidence intervals) for the external load comparisons between acquisition training sessions (ATS). The shaded area, spanning -0.6 to 0.6, represents unmeaningful effect sizes. * Possibly; ** Likely; *** Very Likely; **** Most Likely.